

DISEASE BRIEF Q-FEVER

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Q-Fever: causative organism <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> is a small, obligate intracellular pleomorphic gram-negative bacteria (1). It can be infectious in raw milk for 90-243 days at 4-6 degrees Celsius. It causes an initially mild disease in ruminants but can ultimately result in abortions and still births in cattle, sheep, and goats (2).</p> <p>Some people who get Q-Fever will have no symptoms, others experience sudden headaches, fever, chills, muscle soreness and, in some cases, pneumonia. Some symptoms such as fatigue can be long-lasting and chronic Q-Fever can be deadly if not treated correctly.</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	<p>Q-Fever is listed in the WOAH Terrestrial Animal Health Code.</p> <p>Q-Fever is listed in Regulation (EU) 2016/429 (AHL category E), Reg (EU) 2018/1882, Reg (EU) 2020/2002</p>
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p>Q-fever is distributed worldwide, with the exception of New Zealand.</p> <p>Distribution of Q-fever in Europe: ECDC map available (4). The three countries with the most confirmed cases in 2019 were Spain, France and Germany, however the rate of disease is the same compared to smaller countries in Europe (0.2 per 100,000). Given the largely asymptomatic nature of Q-Fever, establishing the accurate prevalence of Q-Fever in animals in Europe is difficult.</p>
4	Reservoir / main host	<p>Ruminants are the main hosts. The main transmission route for humans is suspected to be through air-borne transmission of the bacteria from animal reservoirs (1,4) and via contaminated sheep wool.</p>
5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	<p>Domestic ruminants (i.e., sheep, goats, and cattle) are considered the main reservoirs of <i>C. burnetii</i>, but cats, dogs, rabbits, birds, and rodents (rats and wild rodents) have also been reported to be implicated in disease spread (1).</p>
6	Vector-borne transmission	<p><i>C. burnetii</i> can be spread via arthropods (ticks) species, however it is rarely found in ticks in most regions of Europe. It is presumed that ticks play a minor role in Q-Fever transmission (1).</p>
7	Environmental transmission	<p><i>C. burnetii</i> can be spread environmentally through wind speed (aerosols downwind from sheep farms). Airborne transmission includes long-distance, indirect transmission of the aerosolized bacteria and direct transmission through inhalation of droplets, aerosols, and dust during</p>

		contact with infected animals and contaminated animal products (6). The highest load of infectious material is found in birth material and aborted fetuses. Spore-like forms of the bacteria are very stable in the environment.
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	Through exposure/inhalation of birth material, urine and faeces, and via contaminated dust.
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	Even though cattle have a similar or higher prevalence than small ruminants, most human outbreaks are associated with goats and sheep. There is clear epidemiological and experimental evidence that the infection is principally transmitted by inhalation of desiccated aerosol particles, and through exposure in the vicinity of infected animals, their reproductive tissues or other animal products, like wool (WOAH report Q-Fever, 2018). Furthermore, since the disease can potentially be transmitted to humans through contaminated milk, pasteurization of milk can prevent infection. Exposure to infected ticks is of minor importance and can be minimized by tick repellent (4).
10	Disease indicators	Except for spontaneous abortions within a herd or flock, initial infection in ruminants is often asymptomatic and not noticed. Humans are often considered as sentinels for the disease, as they may be the first indicator that <i>C. burnetii</i> is impacting a specific locality (6).
11	a) Clinical signs	In cows, ewes and goats, Q-Fever has been associated mostly with late abortion and reproductive disorders such as premature birth, dead or weak offspring. In many cases, ruminants are chronic asymptomatic carriers for the disease and therefore can spread the disease unobserved as long as they are infected.
12	b) Seroconversion	Animals are most frequently seropositive without clinical signs.
13	c) Other disease indicators	Not applicable.
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	Farms of cattle, sheep and goats noticing spontaneous abortions , should test livestock for <i>C. burnetii</i> .
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	PCR, ELISA Culture, Strain testing can be implemented to test for <i>C. burnetii</i> , but no official gold standard test has been developed. Different countries implement different testing methods, which limits comparability.

		<p>PCR testing is effective for evaluation of bacterial shedding. Samples can be taken from vagina, milk, and colostrum. Currently, PCR has become the tool of choice for Q-Fever diagnosis.</p> <p>Three ELISA commercial kits for the diagnosis of Q-Fever in ruminants are currently available (6). ELISA methods are not fully validated and harmonized, yet they are robust and can be automated and are recommended for routine serological testing of animals for Q-Fever.</p> <p>Complement Fixation test (CFT): existing literature illustrates that the relative sensitivity is lowest for the CFT, but conversely it has a high specificity for the high levels of anti-<i>C. burnetii</i> antibodies generated in a Q-Fever aborted herd or flock.</p> <p>Serological testing is useful in clarifying the infection status in herds but provides less certainty about the infection status of individuals or the human health risk.</p> <p>There are currently (2022) two WOAHA Reference Laboratories for Q-fever in Europe (12):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety), France - National Veterinary Research Institute - Department of Cattle and Sheep Diseases, Poland
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<p>Q-Fever is endemic in the EU. Therefore, a surveillance system for early detection should focus on human health risks. A two-step surveillance is suggested with an initial sero-survey to identify regions with high prevalence of Q-fever in ruminants, followed by environmental surveillance in high prevalence regions. In addition, the surveillance based on notifications of abortions, which is already in place in most MS, should be used to detect outbreaks in farms.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Indicator-based surveillance of abortions in ruminants, followed by pathogen detection in aborted fetuses 2. Environmental sampling in high-risk areas (identified, if needed, through sero-survey) <p>Q-Fever may pose a risk for endangered wildlife species in Europe. Among wild endangered species distributed in Europe potentially infected by <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> (diagnosis includes direct detection of pathogen), classified according of their conservation status according (International Union for the Conservation of Nature), 34,7% species are "Near Threatened", 37,4% are "Vulnerable", 15,6% Endangered, and 12,2% Critically Endangered (CR) (13).</p>

		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD VISIT	DEAD	Component name
VECTOR-borne diseases									
Q-FEVER	Ruminants								Serological surveillance of small ruminants can be used to identify high risk areas (to target other activities)
									Indicator-based surveillance of abortions in ruminants
	Ticks								No surveillance component specifically designed
	ENVIRONMENT								Environmental sampling in high-risk areas
	Human								Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope
17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	<p>1. Abortions represent a health risk for people in contact with animals (farmers, abattoir workers, veterinarians...). They are also a risk for environmental contamination of abortion material is not disposed correctly.</p> <p>2. Since the main transmission route is via the environment, environmental testing is an important component for early detection of risk of large outbreaks in humans.</p> <p>If risk areas are not known, a component of serological surveillance in small ruminants can be used as a first step. Serology has the advantage that it indicates the general exposure of the animal population to the pathogen. It can thus very well be used to identify areas with a high prevalence.</p>							
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	<p>Indicator-based surveillance of abortions followed by testing for Q-Fever is currently widespread in European MS. Germany, The Netherlands, France, Bulgaria: the direct detection (by culture or PCR) of <i>C. burnetii</i> in small ruminants and cattle has to be reported to the local veterinary health authority (4,5,7). However, integration with human health authorities is limited. Following the outbreak in the Netherlands, one of the main recommendations of public health authorities was to integrate notification systems. Q-Fever is a notifiable disease in humans within MS of the EU. However, there are also limited rules, relevant to Q-Fever, concerning intra-community trade or import. In some European countries, no national requirement for notification of Q-Fever in ruminants is in place. As of 2010, notification of infected animals is not required in Belgium, Cyprus, Estonia, France, Hungary, Luxembourg, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, UK, Norway (6).</p>							

19	References	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1) WOAH manual on Q-Fever Chapter 3 https://www.woah.org/fileadmin/Home/eng/Health_standards/tahm/3.01.16_Q_FEVER.pdf2) Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung https://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/q_fieber_uebertragung_von_coxiella_burnetii_durch_den_v_erzehr_von_lebensmitteln_tierischer_herkunft_unwahrscheinlich.pdf3) European Commission: Listing of animal diseases https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-07/ah_ahl_btsf_training_20210621_1-3.pdf4) ECDC: Q-Fever in Europe https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/AER-Q-fever-2019.pdf5) ECDC: Q-Fever Risk assessment https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/media/en/publications/Publications/1005_TER_Risk_Assessment_Qfever.pdf6) EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2010.15957) Concept of an Active Surveillance System for Q-Fever in German Small Ruminants—Conflicts Between Best Practices and Feasibility https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7902497/#B398) German veterinary authority notification form https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/tkrmeldpflv_1983/BJNR010950983.html9) IJE Review article Is a One Health Approach Utilized for Q-Fever Control? A Comprehensive Literature Review https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6427780/10) González-Barrio, D.; Jado, I.; Viñuela, J.; García, J.T.; Olea, P.P.; Arce, F.; Ruiz-Fons, F. Investigating the Role of Micromammals in the Ecology of <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> in Spain. <i>Animals</i> 2021, <i>11</i>, 654. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani1103011) https://www.cdc.gov/qfever/symptoms/index.html12) https://www.woah.org/en/what-we-offer/expertise-network/reference-laboratories/#ui-id-3
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20	Additional comments	<p>The initial surveillance component which aims for determining high-risk areas could be replaced with bulk milk serology in dairy sheep and goat farms. Compared to serology, this surveillance component has the disadvantage that it only covers the dairy production sector. However, it could be combined with surveillance for other pathogens such as RVF (for a description of the surveillance, see surveillance component card RVF). For Q-fever, prevalence in bulk milk is not an important indicator of human health risk, because milk plays a minor role for the infection of humans.</p> <p>Coxiella burnetii is a category B bioterrorism agent. Surveillance systems for Q-Fever in humans have been developed with regard to potential bioterrorism.</p>